

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF OTITIS MEDIA WITH EFFUSION ASSOCIATED WITH BADHIRYA (MIXED HEARING LOSS): A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Otitis Media with Effusion (OME), commonly referred to as middle ear effusion, is characterized by the accumulation of non-purulent fluid within the middle ear cavity without acute signs of infection. Persistent middle ear effusion may result in conductive or mixed hearing loss, tinnitus, heaviness in the ear, and impairment in daily activities. In Ayurveda, the clinical presentation of OME can be correlated with *Kapha-Vataja Badhirya*, where *Kapha* causes obstruction in the auditory passages and vitiated *Vata* leads to impairment of auditory perception. **Material and Methods:** A 60-year-old male patient presented to the *Shalaky Tantra* outpatient department with complaints of diminished hearing in the right ear, whistling sound in the ear, heaviness, and pain during swallowing and mouth opening for one month. Previous

treatment with antihistamines and antibiotics provided no significant relief. **Management and Intervention:** The patient was managed with Ayurvedic treatment including *Punarnavashtaka Kwatha*, *Chandraprabha Vati*, *Gokshuradi Guggulu*, *Varunadi Kwatha*, *Virechana Dhoomapana*, local application of *Musta*, *Shunthi*, and *Gokshura Choorna*, along with saline water and *Haridra* gargling. **Result :** Pure Tone Audiometry (PTA) before treatment revealed moderate to moderately severe mixed hearing loss with a PTA average of 56.67 dB in the right ear. Following treatment, the PTA average improved to 23.33 dB. Significant improvement was observed in hearing ability, tinnitus, ear heaviness, and discomfort during swallowing. No adverse drug reactions were reported during treatment or

follow-up. **Conclusion:** This case report suggests that Ayurvedic management may provide beneficial outcomes in Otitis Media with Effusion associated with mixed hearing loss. The combined use of internal medications and local therapeutic procedures helped reduce symptoms and improved auditory function.

KEYWORDS: Otitis Media with Effusion, *Vata-Kapha Badhirya*, Mixed Hearing Loss, *Dhoomapana*.

INTRODUCTION

Hearing plays a vital role in communication, social interaction, education, and overall quality of life. Disorders affecting hearing can lead to emotional, psychological, and functional disturbances in affected individuals. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), hearing impairment is one of the major global health concerns, affecting millions of individuals worldwide.^[1]

Otitis Media with Effusion (OME) is a condition characterized by the collection of sterile fluid in the middle ear cavity without acute suppurative infection. The disease commonly develops secondary to Eustachian tube dysfunction, allergy, upper respiratory tract infections, or chronic inflammation. Persistent middle ear fluid interferes with tympanic membrane mobility and ossicular conduction, resulting in hearing impairment.^[2]

Clinically, patients may present with diminished hearing, ear fullness, tinnitus, discomfort, and difficulty in communication. Long-standing OME may lead to speech impairment, learning difficulties in children, and chronic auditory dysfunction.

In the classical Ayurvedic tradition, otological disorders are categorized under the *Karna Roga*. Within the *Sushruta Samhita Uttara Tantra*, Acharya Sushruta identifies 28 distinct ear pathologies, with *Badhirya* (deafness) regarded as one of the most critical caused predominantly by vitiation of *Vata Dosha*.^[3] *Kapha* involvement produces obstruction in the auditory channels, leading to impaired sound conduction and heaviness in the ear.^[4]

Therefore, the clinical manifestations of OME can be conceptually correlated with *Kapha-Vataja Badhirya*. Therefore, an effective therapeutic approach must prioritize pacifying both *Vata* and *Kapha* while simultaneously addressing underlying inflammation. The management (*Chikitsa Krama*) was planned according to the principle of *Vata-Kapha dosha* predominance of the disease initially *saman chikitsa* pacify the *kapha dosha* and clear *strotorodha* with

dhoomapana and *karnadhupana* Followed by *vata dosha* pacifying *Chikitsa* planned orally and externally accordingly. The present case report highlights the role of Ayurvedic management in a patient suffering from middle ear effusion associated with mixed hearing loss.

CASE REPORT

A 60-year-old male patient visited the outpatient department of *Shalaky Tantra* with complaints of:

- Diminished hearing in the right ear
- Whistling sound in the ear
- Heaviness in the ear
- Pain during swallowing and mouth opening

The symptoms had been present for one month.

The patient had previously taken antihistamines and antibiotics from another healthcare center but did not experience satisfactory relief.

History of Past Illness

No significant past illness was reported.

Family history

No significant family history was noted.

Personal history

Patient has a vegetarian diet. No addiction history of tobacco, pan masala.

Occupation – factory worker. Marital status -married

▪ Bowel: Regular ▪ Appetite: Good ▪ Micturition: 4-6 times/day ▪ Sleep: Sound

Ashtasthana Pareeksha ▪ Nadi: 76/min ▪ Mutra: 4-6 times/day ▪ Mala: 1/day ▪ Jihwa: Aliptha ▪ Shabda: Prakrutha ▪ Sparsha: Anushna Sheetha ▪ Druk: Vikrutha ▪ Akruthi: Madhyam Vitals ▪ Pulse rate: 76/min ▪ Respiratory rate: 25/min ▪ Temp: 98.60 F ▪ BP: 120/84mm of Hg

EAR EXAMINATION

Otoscopic Findings

- External auditory canal appeared normal

- No wax, inflammation, foreign body, or growth observed
- Tympanic membrane showed retraction bilaterally
- Distortion of cone of light was present
- Fluid level was appreciated in the right tympanic membrane

Tuning Fork Tests

- Rinne's test: Air conduction greater than bone conduction bilaterally
- Weber's test: Lateralized to the right ear

Audiological Findings

Pure Tone Audiometry demonstrated moderate to moderately severe mixed hearing loss in the right ear.

Tympanometry

- Right Ear: Type B graph suggestive of middle ear effusion
- Left Ear: Type C graph suggestive of Eustachian tube dysfunction

Therapeutic Intervention

No	Drug	Dose	Anupana	Duration
1	<i>Musta choorna, Sunthi choorna, Gokshura choorna</i>	For L.A	—	Entire treatment period
2	<i>Punarnavashtak Kwath</i>	90 ml After Food	—	1-20 th days
3	<i>Chandraprabha Vati,</i>	2 BD After Food	Luke warm water	Entire treatment period
4	<i>Gokshuradi Guggulu</i>	2 TDS	Luke warm water	Entire treatment period
5	<i>Varunadi kwath</i>		—	35 – 55 th days
6	<i>Virechana Dhoomapan</i>	3 puff	—	4 sitting of 6 days with interval of 4 days
7	Saline water and Harida powder for Gargling	2 times a day	—	Entire treatment period

Pathya Apathya

Patient was strictly advised not to take, cold drinks, ice cream, fast food, fermented food items, spicy food and Direct exposure to wind Patient was advised to take steam inhalation through mouth two times a day with plain water. Intake of lukewarm water for the whole day as a routine

RESULT

Subjective Improvement

- Reduction in heaviness of the ear
- Decrease in tinnitus
- Improvement in hearing ability
- Relief from pain during swallowing

Objective Improvement

The PTA average score improved from 56.67 dB before treatment to 23.33 dB after treatment, indicating significant improvement in hearing function.

No adverse drug reactions or complications were observed during treatment or follow-up.

DISCUSSION

Otitis Media with Effusion develops mainly due to dysfunction of the Eustachian tube, leading to negative middle ear pressure and accumulation of sterile fluid in the middle ear cavity. Persistent fluid interferes with vibration of the tympanic membrane and ossicular movement, resulting in conductive or mixed hearing loss. From the Ayurvedic perspective, the condition can be understood as *Kapha-Vataja Badhirya*. *Kapha Dosha* contributes to obstruction and fluid accumulation within the auditory pathways, while aggravated *Vata* affects the normal transmission of sound.

The treatment protocol in the present case was planned with the objective of reducing *Kapha* accumulation, clearing obstruction in the auditory channels, and normalizing *Vata* function. *Punarnavashtaka Kwatha* possesses *Shothahara* and *Mutrala* properties which may help in reducing inflammatory fluid accumulation. *Chandraprabha Vati* and *Gokshuradi Guggulu* support reduction of swelling and regulation of *Kapha*-related pathology. *Varunadi Kwatha* is known for its *Kapha-Vatahara* action. *Virechana Dhoomapana* was administered to facilitate elimination of *Kapha* from the *Urdhwajatrugata* region. Gargling with saline water and *Haridra* was advised to support local cleansing and improve Eustachian tube function.

The combined internal and external Ayurvedic interventions helped reduce symptoms and improved hearing capacity in this patient. Conventional management of OME often includes antihistamines, antibiotics, decongestants, and surgical interventions such as myringotomy and grommet insertion.^[5] However, recurrence and incomplete relief are frequently observed.

Ayurvedic management may therefore serve as a supportive and non-invasive therapeutic approach in selected cases.

CONCLUSION

The present case report demonstrates that Ayurvedic management may be beneficial in patients suffering from Otitis Media with Effusion associated with mixed hearing loss. Significant improvement was observed in auditory function, tinnitus, heaviness, and associated symptoms following treatment.

The treatment protocol focusing on *Kapha-Vata shamana*, *Srotoshodhana*, *Shothahara* and reduction of middle ear fluid produced encouraging clinical outcomes without adverse effects.

Further clinical studies involving larger sample sizes and long-term follow-up are recommended to validate these observations.

ADR DECLARATION

No any adverse drug reaction was noticed during the treatment and follow up period.

LIMITATION OF STUDY

This is a single case report. Larger clinical studies are necessary to establish standard treatment protocols and evaluate long-term efficacy.

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